

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

International Conference on Teacher Education

INTEGRATING MOBILE PHONES FOR EFFECTIVE EFL LEARNING

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Annotation. *The article explores how using mobile phones in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms can shift the teacher's role from instructor to facilitator. It highlights the importance of student-teacher interaction and collaborative learning, where students work together using technology to share ideas, thoughts, and information effectively.*

Key words: *mobile devices, interaction, facilitator, technology, implement, collaborative learning, teaching techniques.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена использованию технологии мобильных телефонов в классах EFL. Также в работе описывается взаимодействие между учеником и учителем которое является основным, совместным обучением. Он подчеркивает важность взаимодействия учащихся и учителей и совместного обучения, когда учащиеся работают вместе, используя технологии для эффективного обмена идеями, мыслями и информацией.*

Ключевые слова: *мобильные устройства, взаимодействие, координатор, технология, инструмент, совместное обучение, методы обучения.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada EFL sinflarida mobil telefon texnologiyasidan foydalanishga bag'ishlangan. Shuningdek maqolada talaba va o'qituvchi o'zaro hamkorligidagi o'quv jarayoni ifoda etilgan. Bu turdagi ta'lim yo'nalishi maqsadga erishish yo'lidagi g'oya, fikr, his-tuyg'ularini va ma'lumotlarni etkazishni o'z ichiga oladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *mobil qurilmalar, o'zaro aloqa, fasilitator, texnologiya, amalga oshirish, hamkorlikda o'rganish, o'qitish usullari.*

The mobile phones are the energy that drives student-teacher engagement. Students can ask questions, exchange ideas, and practice their English in a relaxed setting by using discussion boards, group note-taking applications, and even instant messaging services. This encourages students to take charge of their education and builds a sense of community.

The major aim of this study is to ascertain how effective the use of Internet capable mobiles is in learning and retaining vocabulary. With the rapid development of modern mobile technology, more and more features and functions are found in mobile phones, which spark more ideas for using them in the language classroom. The following are some practical engagement of mobile phone technology in EFL classes. They offer great evidence that mobile phones can be a very efficient and effective tool of communicative language teaching and learning. [1, 2001] The majority of mobile devices are equipped with a note-taking feature. This feature allows students to take notes on English material they read, hear, or otherwise come across. The teacher may assign the class to look for and gather particular language forms on their phones. It can help students learn continually long after a classroom

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lecture has ended by erasing the boundaries between class time and daily activities. Additionally, almost all phones include memory for images, sounds, and graphics. You can use this memory to download reading and listening resources for kids, who can then transfer them to other media or their phones.

Many books are now published in mobile-friendly formats. Students can use the voice recorder to take notes about the book while they are reading. The books, along with students' reflections, can then be discussed during the class. One of the easiest ways to use a mobile phone for learning is to record samples of the target language by photographing and recording. Students can take pictures of English text by using the camera feature on their mobile phones. They can also collect language samples from TV or radio and make the voice memo. Then they can make a language data base, upload the pictures or audios and share with classmates while practicing the language in groups. One excellent activity in this respect is producing video drama projects with mobile phones. Students are asked to design a project-based video task which combines drama, technology and write English scripts, engage in peer correction and design and produce the video in English, so it is an excellent way to get students to use different communicative functions in English and reinforce their language skills.

Following by some scientist' views Short Message Service (SMS) text messages can be used to send out vocabulary items at spaced intervals, thus increasing student retention.[2,1985]. For example, you could text the words covered in class to encourage students to review them outside the school. By sending out the words many times, you increase the chances that students will remember them eventually. On the other side, text messaging feature of mobile phones can also be used to motivate students' writing interest and improve their writing abilities in English. It's evident that students write a lot when one views writing as any type of textual communication. Circular writing is a good exercise where students work together to compose a story by adding one text message at a time. Until the story is finished, each student writes one or two sentences, forwards it to the following student, who adds another message, and so on. Students are motivated to master the language skill and advance their English communication abilities throughout the process.

Most of the interaction takes place in writing and speaking, so simply asking students to use English instead of their native language produces a great deal of communicative practice in English. In the meantime, teachers can actively use such tools to keep in touch with students or to organize activities online. It proves to be an efficient and enjoyable way for both teachers and learners.

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The following ideas for using mobile phones for second language learning generally focus on developing the four skills and in many cases integrate speaking with listening and reading with writing. The material and activities can be modified to conform to different syllabi and are easily adaptable for different ages, learning levels, and interests. It is important to note that the names of the features used here may not be the same for all mobile phones.

Concept 1: The majority of mobile devices come equipped with a note-taking feature. Request that students take notes on English they read or hear outside of the classroom using this tool, then send you a text message with their notes or bring them to class. Rather than assigning standard homework, assign pupils to find certain language forms; the winner is the one who gathers the most accurate samples. By blurring the lines between class time and everyday activities, this practice helps students avoid the inclination to check out when a lesson in the classroom ends.

Concept 2: Taking pictures of examples of the target language and recording them is one of the simplest methods to use a mobile phone for language learning. Using the camera app on their phones, students can snap images of English text.

They can then make a collage of the images or upload the pictures. If students do not have a data connection (or if you do not want them to incur data costs), they can transfer the pictures to a computer and upload them from there.

Concept 3: The note-recording feature on the majority of phones is capable of gathering linguistic samples from radio or television. The samples that the students have collected allow you to evaluate the language, talk about the location of the collection, and offer comments.

Concept 4: Students can videotape interviews or talks they have with people they meet outside of the classroom. Naturally, privacy concerns must be taken into account, and students must be taught the value of getting permission from their interlocutors before conducting interviews—whether with native speakers or one another. Students can play the interviews and conversations in class for feedback and discussion. I have used this idea to send students on quests to collect information from sources in the community, including from native speakers. Although we used iPods with a microphone, the same task is now easily accomplished with mobile phones. The principle remains the same: try to get students to use the language as much as possible. Using phones for speaking may not seem like an original idea, but one way to encourage reluctant students to start speaking is to establish a language exchange. In these activity two students who want to learn each other’s native language talk in that target language for half of the time. This activity may be

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expensive unless students can use Skype on their mobile phones. Many phones have memory for graphics, photos, and music that you can use to download listening material for your students, who can in turn transfer them to their phones or other media. This could be a recording of your class, a podcast, or course listening materials. In addition to providing hundreds of existing podcasts for English language learners, website will upload your own podcasts to which students can subscribe. Audio books are another source of listening materials.

The official e-portfolio is replaced with an instant reflection that may be downloaded in a number of formats and transmitted. To make sure that students take the exercise seriously, it is crucial to clarify expectations regarding the quantity and frequency of reflection—as well as the reasons behind them. Encourage students to keep a journal of their language use outside of the classroom, noting any difficulties they run into (like a misunderstanding or breakdown in communication) as well as any productive exchanges.

Some teachers use portfolio assessment to give credit for work done outside the classroom, which is also possible with a mobile phone portfolio. In addition, you could encourage students to use the Calendar feature or other productivity tool available on most phones to set goals, deadlines for assignments, and reminders to rehearse material covered in class. Some students may be reluctant to share private information with others, some may refuse to share the phones in-group activities, and some may use mobile phones to violate others' privacy by taking photos, making video recordings, or even spread some private information through internet. Therefore, it is very important to consider issues of privacy before using mobile phones in class. Teachers need to explain to students what the teaching objectives are and find out if they have any concerns about using their phone for learning activities. To sum up, we can say that the clear rules need to be nailed down about when and how mobile phones can be used to avoid inappropriate purposes and behaviors. The mobile phone technology engagement is an effective option for the language teachers in EFL classes.

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